

1 **GABA signaling functions in lineage commitment in the human embryo.**

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6 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
7 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here critical changes in
8 GABAergic signaling during lineage commitment in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.

9 Citations

- 10 1. Wang, D.D., Kriegstein, A.R. and Ben-Ari, Y., 2008. GABA regulates stem cell proliferation before
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